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Simulation of high temperature proton exchange fuel cells with damaged areas in the catalyst layer.

R. Losantos,^a R. Mustata^a, M. Montiel^{a,b}, L. Valiño^a.

^a Instituto de Carboquímica ICB, CSIC, C/Miguel Luesma Castán, 4 50018, Zaragoza, Spain.

^b Fundación Agencia Aragonesa para la Investigación y el Desarrollo (ARAID), Av. de Ranillas 1-D, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain
raul.losantos@csic.es

Computational simulation is emerging as a fundamental tool in studying and improving the efficiency and durability of fuel cells. In these complex devices, expressing the electrochemical and transport processes occurring in the catalytic layers and the membrane presents a significant challenge, necessitating the integration of precise physical equations with semi-empirical models. Most of the 3D simulation models for hydrogen fuel cells describe the transport of protons approximating its behavior to an orthonormal crossover to the catalytic layers. Also, when addressing the transport, the stabilization of the reversible potential is achieved through the application of the Nernst equation or a fixed value [1]. This approach has proven to be highly valuable across diverse operational scenarios [2]; however, a reduction in precision is observed under specific circumstances, notably when simulating local degradation conditions within the catalytic layers.

The proposed model considers half-reactions that occur at each electrode separately, rather than assuming a single overall reaction for the entire cell, which is the traditional approach [3]. Specifically, the reversible potentials of the semi-reactions occurring in each of the catalytic layers are calculated. This includes the formation of water at the cathode from oxygen and protons crossing the membrane, as well as the dissociation reaction of hydrogen into protons at the anode. The outcome is a potential distribution for the semi-reactions in each catalytic layer, computed in accordance with local operating conditions. These potentials are employed to obtain the boundary conditions utilized in computing both the distribution of protonic potential and the proton flux within the membrane. In this study, the separate electrochemical model has been incorporated into the 3D simulation model developed by Losantos et al. [4]. The objective is to investigate proton transport within the membrane under diverse operational and locally degraded membrane conditions. The results of this new approach are then compared to those obtained using the previous methodology, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the proton transport phenomena in the membrane.

Figure 1: (a) Example of heterogeneous local degradation in a fuel cell. (b) Representation of channel geometry and proton flux performance on the membrane under local degradation conditions. (c) Section of a degraded local region, where the proton potential distribution and the behaviour of the proton flux can be observed.

References

- [1] M. Arif, S. Cheung, J. Andrews, *Energy & Fuels*. Volume 34. (2020).
- [2] L. Valiño, R. Mustata, L. Dueñas, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, Volume 39. (2014) Pages 4030-4036.
- [3] F. Barbir, *Fuel cell basic chemistry and thermodynamics*, Volume nr. (2013) Pages 28-29.
- [4] R. Losantos, M. Montiel, R. Mustata, F. Zorrilla, L. Valiño, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, Volume 47. (2022) Pages 4814-4826.